

Effect of Ag on the precipitation stability in Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloy: First-principles calculations, Calphad modeling and experimental validation

Wei shao^{1,*}, Witold Chrominski¹, Mark Fedorov¹, Chenying Shi², Javier LLorca^{2,3,*} and Jan S. Wróbel^{1,*}

¹Faculty of Materials Science and Engineering, Warsaw University of Technology, ul. Wołoska 141, 02-507, Warsaw, Poland

²IMDEA Materials Institute, C/Eric Kandel 2, 28906 Madrid, Spain

³Department of Materials Science. Polytechnic University of Madrid/Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. E. T. S. de Ingenieros de Caminos, 28040 Madrid, Spain.

Abstract: The Gibbs free energy of different phases in the Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloy system was determined by combining first-principles calculations, cluster expansion method and Monte Carlo simulations. This information was used to develop a thermodynamic database of the Al-Mg-Si-Ag system, enabling accurate determination of phase stability and phase distribution. The analysis of short-range order parameters showed that the solute cluster was dominated by Mg-Si co-clusters in Al-Mg-Si alloys, while Mg-Ag co-clusters formed prior to the Mg-Si-Ag clusters when the Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloy is quenched from high temperature. Experimental observations by means of transmission electron microscopy confirmed the existence of such clusters. The addition of Ag also modified the crystal structure of Guinier-Preston zones, whose composition was $Al_{1-z}Ag_z$, $Al_{1-x-z}Mg_xAg_z$ and Mg_xAg_z . In contrast, the crystal structure of metastable β'' and stable β phases was not influenced by the presence of Ag. Phase diagram calculations of the Al-Mg-Si-Ag system revealed the existence of a fcc single-phase in Al-Ag, Al-Mg, Ag-Mg binary and Al-Ag-Mg ternary systems. In the Al-rich region of the quaternary system, two-phase regions fcc + β and fcc + β'/β'_{Ag} were observed. As temperature increases, the fcc + β'/β'_{Ag} two-phase region gradually transforms into the fcc + β two-phase region. These results reveal the thermodynamic stability of metastable precipitate and, in certain cases, elucidate compositional changes in precipitates during the aging process.

Keywords: Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloys; First-principles calculations; Monte Carlo simulations; Calphad; Transmission electron microscopy

1. Introduction

Al-Mg-Si alloys are widely used in construction, automotive engineering, and aviation industries due to their good corrosion resistance, excellent formability and weldability [1,2]. The mechanical properties of Al-Mg-Si alloys are controlled by the type, dimension, and distribution of nano-sized precipitates that form during aging at different temperatures and times [3,4]. Therefore, it is useful to study the precipitate evolution of Al-Mg-Si alloys to gain insight into their age-hardening response.

The precipitation sequence in the Al-Mg-Si alloys has been reported as [5,6]: supersaturated solid solution (SSSS) \rightarrow Mg-Si co-clusters \rightarrow GP zones $\rightarrow \beta'' \rightarrow \beta' \rightarrow \beta(\text{Mg}_2\text{Si})$. The main hardening phase in the peak hardness condition is the needle-like β'' , which has a monoclinic unit cell with $a=15.16 \text{ \AA}$, $b=4.05 \text{ \AA}$, $c=6.74 \text{ \AA}$ and $\beta=105.3^\circ$ [7]. The chemical composition of β'' was initially determined to be Mg_5Si_6 using high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) and electron diffraction (ED) [8]. Subsequently, Ninive provided the atomistic insight into the β'' phase by scanning transmission electron microscopy with high-resolution high-angle annular dark field (HAADF-STEM), and proposed that the most likely composition of β'' was $\text{Al}_3\text{Mg}_4\text{Si}_4$ [9]. Another possible composition of β'' reported was $\text{Al}_2\text{Mg}_5\text{Si}_4$ [10]. Hence, the composition of β'' is still a subject of controversy. β' precipitates form after β'' precipitates in the ageing sequence. The $\beta(\text{Mg}_2\text{Si})$ phase with anti-fluorite (CaF_2) structure is formed at equilibrium [5].

Early investigations have demonstrated that the strength of Al-Mg-Si alloys was enhanced after aging [11], and that considerable precipitation strengthening can be achieved by adding microalloying elements [12,13]. Ding et al. [14] indicated that the addition of Cu suppresses the precipitation of β'' and results in the formation of quaternary phases (QP) during aging. Therefore, the precipitation sequence of Al-Mg-Si alloys with Cu is: SSSS \rightarrow atomic clusters \rightarrow GP zones $\rightarrow \beta''$, QP1, QP2, C ($\text{Mg}_4\text{Al}_1\text{Si}_{3+x}\text{Cu}_{1-x}$, $x \sim 0.3$) \rightarrow Q' ($\text{Al}_3\text{Cu}_2\text{Mg}_9\text{Si}_7$), QP2, C \rightarrow Q ($\text{Al}_4\text{Cu}_2\text{Mg}_8\text{Si}_7$), Si. Ding et al. [15] found that relatively high concentrations (3 wt.%) of Zn could enhance the age hardening response of Al-0.99Mg-0.54Si (wt. %) alloy by forming GP (II)-zones of $\eta\text{-MgZn}_2$ and its precursor.

Compared with Zn and Cu, Ag not only significantly improves the age-hardening response and hardening kinetics of Al-Mg-Si alloys during artificial aging, but also ensures relatively low strength in the natural aging, thereby providing a good balance between formability and bake-hardening potential [16]. Ag atoms could enter Mg-Si clusters and refine the distribution of

clusters during the early aging, which resulted in a finer and denser distribution of β'' to improve the peak hardness for these alloys [17]. Marioara et al. [18] observed through HAADF-STEM that the addition of Ag transforms the structure of β' from Mg_9Si_5 to $Al_3Mg_3Si_2Ag$. More recently, Weng et al. [19] found that another quaternary phase $Q_{Ag}' Al_3Mg_3SiAg_2$ structure may also be formed, and the precipitate sequence was: $SSSS \rightarrow$ atomic clusters \rightarrow GP zones $\rightarrow \beta'' \rightarrow \beta', \beta'_{Ag1}, \beta'_{Ag2}, Q_{Ag}' \rightarrow \beta, Ag$.

Although many studies of the precipitate phases have been reported [18-21], complete crystal structure information of these phases is not always available or unambiguous. Specifically, the solute clustering behavior was not examined, which is essential for understanding the early stages of precipitation and plays a vital role in determining the thermodynamic stability and strengthening mechanisms of Al-Mg-Si(-Ag) alloys. The GP zones are the precursors and nucleation core of the main strengthening phase β'' , while the effect of Ag on the atomic structures of GP zones and β'' phase formed at the early and peak aging stage is still unknown. Additionally, some studies indicated that structure of β was not influenced by Ag atoms [19,22], while Zhang et al. [23] revealed that Ag atoms entered the crystal structure of β by replacing Si atoms in the corners of the unit cell. The remarkable solubility of Ag in β (Mg_2Si) has been confirmed by Udono et al. [24] and Prytuliak et al. [25]. However, it is very difficult to answer these questions in the Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloys only from experimental observations.

Currently, the phase stability for a system is typically evaluated using thermodynamic databases (TDBs) obtained through the Calphad (calculation of phase diagrams) method [26]. However, due to the limitation of slow kinetics at low temperature and incomplete thermodynamic information in some phases [25-27], the TDBs available may not be accurate for alloys within the complex Al-Mg-Si-Ag system. Within this framework, the objective of this investigation is to develop a strategy that integrates first-principles calculations and the cluster expansion (CE) method coupled with statistical mechanics principles to construct the Al-Mg-Si-Ag TDB without relying on experiments [30,31]. To this end, the Gibbs free energies of each phase in the system are obtained as a function of temperature and composition from the formation enthalpies at 0 K calculated from density functional theory (DFT) and thermodynamic properties - formation enthalpies and entropy - at finite temperatures obtained from Monte Carlo (MC) simulations [32,33]. These TDBs for the Al-Mg-Si-Ag system are implemented into the OpenCalphad software [32-34]. They allow to determine the stability region of key precipitate phases $\beta'', \beta', \beta'_{Ag}$ and β , as well as phase coexistence and their fractions.

The atomic structure and composition of GP zones are also determined based on this methodology. The simulation results were validated through STEM-HAADF. Moreover, the accurate TDB for this quaternary alloy will facilitate the prediction of thermodynamic properties in binary and ternary systems involving Al, Mg, Si and Ag atoms. It also provides a robust foundation for extrapolating to more complex Al-Mg-Si-based alloy systems, overcoming the limitations of experimental approaches due to the extensive number of measurements required to explore the entire compositional space.

2. Methodology

2.1 DFT calculations

DFT calculations were carried out in the Vienna ab initio simulation package (VASP) [37], using the projector augmented wave (PAW) method [38]. Exchange-correlation is treated in the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) of Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) [39]. The electronic configurations considered are $3s^23p^1$ for Al, $2p^63s^2$ for Mg, $3s^23p^2$ for Si, and $4d^{10}5s^1$ for Ag, respectively. Convergence tests indicated that a cutoff of 400 eV is sufficient to ensure total energy differences are less than 1 meV/atom. The Γ -centered Monkhorst-Pack mesh [40] of k -points in the Brillouin zone, with the k -mesh spacing of 0.02 \AA^{-1} , corresponding to a $12 \times 12 \times 12$ k -point mesh for a fcc conventional unit cell. The total energy convergence criterion is set to 10^{-5} eV/cell, and force components are relaxed to 10^{-3} eV/Å. All structures are fully relaxed concerning volume as well as cell-internal and -external coordinates.

2.2 Cluster expansion

The formation enthalpies, H_{form} , of a set of $\text{Al}_x\text{Mg}_y\text{Si}_z\text{Ag}_{1-x-y-z}$ configurations that comprise the whole composition range of the system are calculated as [41]

$$H_{\text{form}}^{\text{Al}_x\text{Mg}_y\text{Si}_z\text{Ag}_{1-x-y-z}} = E_{\text{tot}}^{\text{Al}_x\text{Mg}_y\text{Si}_z\text{Ag}_{1-x-y-z}} - xE_{\text{fcc}}^{\text{Al}} - yE_{\text{diamond}}^{\text{Si}} - zE_{\text{hcp}}^{\text{Mg}} - (1-x-y-z)E_{\text{fcc}}^{\text{Ag}} \quad (1)$$

where x , y and z are atomic fractions of Al, Si and Mg in a given configuration, respectively.

$E_{\text{tot}}^{\text{Al}_x\text{Mg}_y\text{Si}_z\text{Ag}_{1-x-y-z}}$ is the total energy per atom of $\text{Al}_x\text{Mg}_y\text{Si}_z\text{Ag}_{1-x-y-z}$ after relaxation, $E_{\text{fcc}}^{\text{Al}}$, $E_{\text{fcc}}^{\text{Ag}}$,

$E_{\text{diamond}}^{\text{Si}}$, and $E_{\text{hcp}}^{\text{Mg}}$ are the energies of the stable phases for Al and Ag with fcc lattice, Si with

diamond lattice, and Mg with hcp lattice, respectively.

In the CE formalism [40-42], the formation enthalpy can be parametrized as a polynomial in the occupational variables σ :

$$H_{form}(\vec{\sigma}) = \sum_{\omega,n,s} J_{\omega,n}^{(s)} m_{\omega,n}^{(s)} \langle \varphi(\vec{\sigma}) \rangle_{\omega,n}^{(s)} \quad (2)$$

where $\vec{\sigma} = \{\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \dots, \sigma_N\}$ is the vector of occupation variables that define the atomic species in lattice site i in a quaternary system ($\sigma_i = 0, 1, 2, 3$) with 0 for Al, 1 for Mg, 2 for Si and 3 for Ag, following the methodology previously applied to the quaternary Fe-Cr-Mn-Ni system [45]. The summation is performed over all the clusters, distinct under symmetry operations in the studied lattice, represented by the following parameters: ω and n are the cluster size (the number of lattice points in the cluster) and its label (related to the maximal distance between two atoms in the cluster), respectively. (s) is the decoration of cluster by a point function $\gamma_{j,K}(\sigma_i)$. $J_{\omega,n}^{(s)}$ represents the effective cluster interaction (ECI) coefficient corresponding to the same (s) decorated cluster. $m_{\omega,n}^{(s)}$ denotes the site multiplicity of the decorated clusters. $\langle \varphi(\vec{\sigma}) \rangle_{\omega,n}^{(s)}$ is the cluster basis function, which is expressed as a product of orthonormal point functions $\gamma_{j,K}(\sigma_i)$ over all sites included in the specific cluster described by ω and n [42]:

$$\langle \varphi(\vec{\sigma}) \rangle_{\omega,n}^{(s)} = \gamma_{j_1 K}(\sigma_1) \gamma_{j_2 K}(\sigma_2) \cdots \gamma_{j_\omega K}(\sigma_\omega) \quad (3)$$

where $j_i = (0, 1, 2, 3)$ has a similar meaning to σ_i , indicating which type of atom is located on the lattice site i that belongs to the cluster. K is the number of alloy components, which is equal to 4 in our system. The cluster basis functions of each pair of clusters, α and β , should satisfy $\langle \varphi(\vec{\sigma})_\alpha^{(s)}, \varphi(\vec{\sigma})_\beta^{(s)} \rangle = 0$ if they are different and $\langle \varphi(\vec{\sigma})_\alpha^{(s)}, \varphi(\vec{\sigma})_\alpha^{(s)} \rangle = 1$ if they are identical. This is achieved by $\gamma_{j,K}(\sigma_i)$ as [34,44]:

$$\gamma_{j,K}(\sigma_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } j = 0, \\ -\cos\left(2\pi\left[\frac{j_i}{2}\right]\frac{\sigma_i}{K}\right) & \text{if } j > 0 \text{ and odd,} \\ -\sin\left(2\pi\left[\frac{j_i}{2}\right]\frac{\sigma_i}{K}\right) & \text{if } j > 0 \text{ and even} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $\left[\frac{j_i}{2}\right]$ denotes the ceiling function - rounding up to the closest integer.

The optimal values of ECIs are calculated to minimize the Cross-Validation (CV) Score between H_{form}^{DFT} and H_{form}^{CE} through the structure inversion method, as implemented in the ATAT package [43]:

$$CV = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (E_i^{DFT} - E_i^{CE'})^2 / N} \quad (5)$$

Where $E_i^{\text{CE}'}$ is the predicted energy of i th structure by fitting CE energies from DFT, and excluding the i th structure.

2.3 Monte Carlo simulations

At finite temperatures, the stability of the different phases may change significantly due to entropic contributions [46,47]. In this work, we mainly focus on configurational entropy as the strongest contribution to the Gibbs free energy of formation, G_{form} . G_{form} for a given composition at finite temperature can be calculated by performing a canonical MC simulation - the chemical composition and number of atoms are fixed - within the CE formalism for each lattice:

$$G_{form}^{MC}(\vec{\sigma}, T) = H_{form}(\vec{\sigma}, T) - TS_{conf}(\vec{\sigma}, T) \quad (6)$$

where formation enthalpy $H_{form}(\vec{\sigma}, T)$ is calculated from eq. (2). The configurational entropy $S_{conf}(\vec{\sigma}, T)$ per site is calculated from the specific heat $C(\vec{\sigma}, T')$ by thermodynamic integration as [48]

$$S_{conf}(\vec{\sigma}, T) = \int_0^T \frac{C(\vec{\sigma}, T')}{T'} dT' \quad (7)$$

where $C(\vec{\sigma}, T')$ can be obtained from the fluctuations of the formation enthalpy in MC simulations at temperature T' , by using the expression [48]:

$$C(\vec{\sigma}, T') = \frac{\langle H_{form}^2(\vec{\sigma}, T') \rangle - \langle H_{form}(\vec{\sigma}, T') \rangle^2}{T'^2} \quad (8)$$

where $\langle H_{form}(\vec{\sigma}, T') \rangle$ and $\langle H_{form}^2(\vec{\sigma}, T') \rangle$ are the mean and mean-squared average formation enthalpies, respectively, which describe the variance of $H_{form}(\vec{\sigma}, T')$. They are computed by averaging all the MC steps at the accumulation stage for a given temperature, as in [48].

Canonical MC simulations were performed using the ATAT package separately for fcc, CaF₂ (β), β' and β'_{Ag} lattices, because these phases were found in the Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloys [19]. Supercells were generated at 1 at. % intervals over the whole composition range using the special quasi-random structure (SQS) method [49], comprising $10 \times 10 \times 10$ supercells with 4000 atoms for fcc, $5 \times 5 \times 5$ supercells with 1500 atoms for β , $5 \times 3 \times 2$ supercells with 840 atoms for β' , and $5 \times 3 \times 6$ supercells with 810 atoms for β'_{Ag} . For each composition, MC simulations are performed starting from a high-temperature disordered state at $T = 1000$ K. The alloy is then cooled down to 10 K within the temperature step of $\Delta T = 20$ K. At each

temperature, a MC simulation includes 3000 passes for equilibrium and thermodynamic averages.

The phase boundary in binary systems can be determined by the common tangent of Gibbs free energy of formation G_{form} , and then the fraction of the considered phases as functions of concentration can be calculated by using the lever rule [50,51]. In the case of multicomponent Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloys, the calculation of fractions of both phases in a four-dimensional composition space cannot be achieved by the application of one common tangent [34]. Instead, the well-established Calphad method provides robust algorithms for calculating multi-component equilibria, which are essential for evaluating the corresponding phase fractions [35,52].

2.4 Development of thermodynamic databases

The Gibbs free energy of formation for a solid solution phase within the framework of Calphad can be expressed as [53]

$$G_{form} = G_{ref} + G_{ideal} + G_{xs} \quad (9)$$

where $G_{ref} = \sum_{i=1}^4 x_i^0 G_i$ is the reference energy of pure elements (Al, Mg, Si and Ag) for the stable phase. $G_{ideal} = -TS_{ideal}$ describes the contribution to the Gibbs free energy from ideal random mixing of the constituents on the crystal lattice. $S_{ideal} = -R \sum_{i=1}^4 x_i \ln x_i$, where R is the gas constant, and x_i the mole fraction of component i .

G_{xs} is the excess Gibbs free energy of formation, describing the influence of non-ideal mixing behaviour on the thermodynamic properties of a solution phase. G_{xs} is usually described by the semi-empirical Redlich-Kister (RK) polynomial [54,55]:

$$G_{xs} = x_s^2 G + x_s^3 G + \dots = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n x_i x_j \sum_v L_{i,j} (x_i - x_j)^v + \sum_{i=1}^{n-2} \sum_{j=i+1}^{n-1} \sum_{k=j+1}^n x_i x_j x_k (u_i L_i + u_j L_j + u_k L_k) + \dots \quad (10)$$

$$u_i = x_i + \frac{1 - x_i - x_j - x_k}{3} \quad (11)$$

$$u_j = x_j + \frac{1 - x_i - x_j - x_k}{3} \quad (12)$$

$$u_k = x_k + \frac{1 - x_i - x_j - x_k}{3} \quad (13)$$

where ^{xs2}G and ^{xs3}G are binary and ternary excess terms, respectively. L is the interaction parameter between components and v is the maximum power used in the optimization.

It should be noted that complex phases are usually modelled using the compound energy formalism (CEF) in the Calphad methodology. Thus, β' and β'_{Ag} phases in Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloys are described by $(Al,Mg)_{18}(Si,Ag)_{10}$ and $(Al,Mg)_6(Si,Ag)_3$, respectively. Therefore, G_{ref} is expressed as

$$G_{ref} = \sum_{s,t=1,2} y_i^s y_j^t G_{i,j}^{s,t} \quad (i=Al, Mg; j=Si, Ag) \quad (14)$$

where y is denoted as site fraction and defined as the composition of each constituent in the sublattice s . The $G_{i,j}^{s,t}$ represents the Gibbs free energy of formation of compounds where each sublattice is occupied by the same constituent, such as $Al_{18}Si_{10}$ and Al_6Si_3 .

In this work, TDBs based only on the results of MC simulations obtained using the DFT-based CE models were generated for fcc, β , β' and β'_{Ag} in the Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloys using sqs2tdb tool in ATAT package [56]. Therefore, two important details have to be pointed out in the fitting: (1) temperature dependence of G_{form} is contained in the G_{ref} supplied from SGTE databases in the traditional Calphad model [57], which contradicts our objective to create TDBs just from DFT simulations, so the SGTE database has not been used. (2) Excess Gibbs free energy of formation G_{xs} does not include quaternary interactions (^{xs4}G) in the sqs2tdb fitting because they would not contribute to the description of the Gibbs free energies of the phases [58]. Finally, the TDBs obtained from the MC simulations were used to calculate the phase equilibrium diagram using OpenCalphad at each temperature using the corresponding TDB [34].

2.5 Experiments and microstructural observation

In order to verify the actual phase transformations, an ingot with chemical composition Al 0.89Mg 0.96Si 0.15Ag (at. %) was prepared by mould casting from pure elements (> 99.9% purity). After homogenization and recrystallization at 520 °C, billets were heated up to 520°C during one hour followed by water quenching. Afterwards, they were artificially aged at 160°C in a furnace. The results of heat treatment were evaluated on the basis of hardness measurements. Three samples, aged during 0.5h, 2h and 12h were selected as representative of the precipitation evolution to support calculations in this study. They stand for the early stages (clustering), the beginning of hardness stabilization and the peak hardness, respectively.

Thin foils for microscopic evaluation were prepared with convention electrochemical polishing of 3 mm discs. A solution of nitric acid in methanol has been used for this purpose. STEM-HAADF observation (collection angle range of 45-200 mrad) was carried out in C_s -corrected ThermoFisherScientific Spectra 200 microscope. Beam current below 25 pA has been kept during the observations and energy dispersive spectroscopic analysis in order to maintain the stability of clusters and precipitates.

3. Results

3.1 Phases of interest

The stable and metastable phases in the Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloys - according to the information in the literature[5,8,19,59] - are listed in Table. 1. Their crystal structures are depicted in Fig. 1. Based on our previous experience [60,61], some phases with complex structure can be treated as a distorted configuration on a simpler lattice. Al has a fcc lattice (Fig.1(a)). The β'' (Mg_5Si_6) (Fig. 1(b)) also presents a fcc lattice, where the lattice vector $b_{\beta''}$ of β'' is parallel to the [001] axis of α -Al, and the other two lattice vectors of β'' are defined by $a_{\beta''}=2a_{Al}+3b_{Al}$ (the [230] direction in α -Al) and $c_{\beta''}=-\frac{3}{2}a_{Al}+\frac{1}{2}Al$ (the $[3\bar{1}0]$ direction in α -Al). However, the crystal structure of β'' is not uniquely determined from Refs. [8-10], which may contain a certain fraction of Al. β' (Mg_9Si_5) (Fig.1(c)) has a hexagonal unit cell, and there are multiple orientation relationships between α -Al and β' [62]. β'_{Ag1} (Fig.1d) and β'_{Ag2} (Fig.1(f)) have a hexagonal unit cell that is similar to that of β' phase, while their lattice parameter along the a-axis is slightly different from the corresponding direction in β' . β (Mg_2Si) has a CaF_2 structure. It is worth noting that all phases, except for the equilibrium phases β - Mg_2Si and Si, are metastable.

Table 1. Structural information of the different phases in the Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloys.

Composition	Symmetry	Lattice parameters (Å)	phase
Al	Fm $\bar{3}$ m	$a = b = c = 4.05$	α
Mg_5Si_6	C2/m	$a=15.16, b=4.05, c=6.74$ $\beta=105.3^\circ$	β''
Mg_9Si_5	P6 $_3$ /m	$a = b = 7.15, c = 12.15$ $\alpha = \beta = 90^\circ, \gamma = 120^\circ$	β'
$Al_3Mg_3Si_2Ag$	P62m	$a = b = 6.9, c = 4.05$ $\alpha = \beta = 90^\circ, \gamma = 120^\circ$	β'_{Ag1}
$Al_3Mg_3SiAg_2$	P62m	$a = b = 7.2, c = 4.05$	β'_{Ag2}

Fig. 1. Crystal structure of the different phases in the Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloys: (a) α (Al). (b) β'' (Mg_5Si_6) (c) Mg_9Si_5 . (d) $\beta'_{\text{Ag}1}$ ($\text{Al}_3\text{Mg}_3\text{Si}_2\text{Ag}$). (e) $\beta'_{\text{Ag}2}$ ($\text{Al}_3\text{Mg}_3\text{SiAg}_2$). (f) β (Mg_2Si). Al, Mg, Si and Ag atoms are indicated by blue, orange, purple and grey spheres, respectively

3.2 Phase stability

4809 configurations with the fcc lattice were enumerated using the ATAT package, and their energies were calculated based on DFT. 3704 configurations were chosen to fit the CE after relaxation by excluding configurations where the deformation is larger than 10% [63]. The formation enthalpies of configurations with a fcc lattice are depicted in Fig. 2. Multiple calculations were performed for several concentrations, but only the configurations with the lowest formation enthalpy H_{form} are shown. It should be noted that the H_{form} of both Si and Mg is larger than 0, because their reference structures are diamond and hcp, respectively. The H_{form} for configurations containing Al, Mg and Ag atoms is lower than those configurations containing Si atoms, meaning that there are repulsive interactions between Si and the three other atoms. In the end, all configurations that did not degenerate to another lattice after relaxation were used to fit the ECI coefficients in the CE model using 30 pair clusters, 28 triplet clusters and 15 quadruplet clusters. The CV score of the fcc CE was 0.0106 eV/atom. The detailed information of the CE, including cluster size, multiplicity as well as the actual values of ECIs for each cluster can be found in Table S1 in the Supplementary Material.

Fig. 2 Formation enthalpies of configurations with fcc lattice with respect to fcc Al and Ag, diamond Si and hcp Mg according to Eq. (1).

The formation of β'_{Ag1} and β'_{Ag2} is due to Ag atoms replacing different Si atomic sites in the QP lattice (a hexagonal network of Si atomic columns) following the analysis of Weng et al. [19]. Thus, it can be assumed that Ag and Si atoms preferentially occupy the same sublattice in the β' and β'_{Ag} lattices, whereas Al and Mg atoms are located on a different, common sublattice. Based on this, 782 configurations with β' lattice and 646 configurations with β'_{Ag} lattice were generated enumerated using the ATAT package, respectively. Their energies were calculated using DFT and 719 configurations with β' lattice and 451 configurations with β'_{Ag} lattice were chosen to fit the CE. The configurations with the lowest H_{form} for each concentration are shown in Figs. 3(a) and 3(b). β' (Mg_9Si_5) is a metastable phase formed during precipitation hardening of Al-Mg-Si alloys, as shown from experiments [64]. The H_{form} decreased with the incorporation of Ag in the Mg-rich Al-Mg-Si-Ag region, meaning that the addition of Ag into β' is energetically favorable for the formation of new phases (Figs. 3(a) and 3(b)). Additionally, the incorporation of Ag also promotes the small solubility of Al in the β' , which is in agreement with experiments [65]. The ECI coefficients in the CE model for β' lattice were fitted using 24 pair clusters, 17 triplet clusters and 8 quadruplet clusters with a CV score of 0.0088 eV/atom). The ECI coefficients in the CE model for β'_{Ag} lattice were fitted using 18 pair clusters, 15 triplet clusters and 24 quadruplet clusters with a CV score of 0.0059 eV/atom. The detailed information of the CE as well as the actual values of the ECI coefficients of each cluster can be found in Table S2 and Table S3 in the Supplementary Material.

Fig. 3 Formation enthalpies of configurations with β' lattice (a) and β'_{Ag} (b), with respect to fcc Al and Ag, diamond Si and hcp Mg according to Eq. (1).

4297 configurations from β (that is CaF_2) lattice were enumerated using the ATAT package, and their energies were calculated using DFT. 2585 configurations that remained with this structure were chosen to fit the CE. The configurations with the lowest H_{form} for each concentration were shown in Fig. 4. As expected, β (Mg_2Si) is on the convex hull because it is known to be a stable phase in Al-Mg-Si and Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloys [66,67]. Although the H_{form} of Mg-rich Mg-Si-Ag region is much lower than that of other regions, the incorporation of Ag atom into Mg_2Si is difficult because the H_{form} of all configurations with this lattice is larger than that of Mg_2Si combined with Mg and Si atoms. Thus, the crystal structure of Mg_2Si is not influenced by the addition of Ag. The ECI coefficients in the CE model for β lattice were fitted using 40 pair clusters and 30 triplet clusters with a CV score of 0.0089 eV/atom. The detailed information of the CE as well as the actual values of the ECI coefficients of each cluster can be found in Table S4 in the Supplementary Material.

Fig. 4 Formation enthalpies of configurations with β (CaF_2) lattice with respect to fcc Al and Ag, diamond Si and hcp Mg according to Eq. (1).

3.3 Phase stability of the Al-Mg-Si-Ag system at 0 K

The formation enthalpies, H_{form} , of configurations with four different lattices in six binary systems were compared using the same reference energy (fcc Al and Ag, diamond Si and hcp Mg), and they are plotted in Fig. 5. All ground states are connected by a grey line. It should be noted that some lattice sites can be occupied by either Al or Mg, or by Si or Ag in the β' and β'_{Ag} lattices. Thus, only the H_{form} of end member configuration for them is shown in Fig. 5. Here, the H_{form} of β' with composition Mg_6Si_4 is also shown in Fig. 5, since it has been reported as β' in Refs. [65-67]. In Ag-Al and Al-Mg systems, the configuration with the fcc lattice is the most stable for the whole composition range. Especially, the H_{form} of all configurations in the Al-Mg system - except for AlMg (-0.0033 eV/atom) - are positive but close to 0. This indicates there is a thermodynamic driving force for phase separation at low temperatures and suggests the possible existence of a miscibility gap in the Al-Mg system. In Ag-Mg system, except for $AgMg_2$ with β'_{Ag} lattice appearing on the convex hull, all stable ground states are composed of configurations with fcc lattice, where the $MgAg_3$ (AuCu₃ structure) has been reported in the Ag-Mg phase diagram [71]. The H_{form} of all configurations is much larger than 0 in Ag-Si and Al-Si systems, which means that there is no stable structure. It was also confirmed in the available Al-Si and Ag-Si phase diagrams that they do not contain intermetallic phases [72]. In the Mg-Si system, only the stable Mg_2Si (β) lies on the convex hull, indicating that it is the only thermodynamically stable compound at 0 K. Mg_5Si_6 (β'') and Mg_9Si_5 (β') lattices are metastable because they lie above the convex hull. This result is consistent with the calculated results reported by Huan et al. [73]. Metastable Mg_5Si_6 (β'') and Mg_9Si_5 (β') are unlikely to be stabilized through vibrational entropy at elevated temperatures since their formation enthalpies are significantly above the convex hull at their respective Si composition. Nevertheless, they may form as kinetically favored intermediate phases during the aging process of Al-Mg-Si alloys, especially under conditions of limited atomic diffusion and local solute supersaturation.

Fig. 5. Formation enthalpies H_{form} computed based on DFT for (a) Ag-Al. (b) Ag-Mg. (c) Ag-Si. (d) Al-Mg. (e) Al-Si and (f) Mg-Si binary structures underlying fcc, β , β'/β'_{Ag} lattice. Green, orange and purple circles represent configurations with fcc, β , β'/β'_{Ag} lattice, respectively. The grey line is the convex hull in the whole binary system.

3.4 Possible structures of GP zones

GP zones are typically considered as regions enriched with solute atoms and fully coherent with the Al matrix. Spherical GP zones in Al-Mg-Si alloy have been reported to be layered structures

composed of alternating Mg and Si atomic layers arranged periodically along the Al (100) plane [74,75]. However, it remains unclear whether the addition of Ag alters the structure of these GP zones. Therefore, configurations with a fcc lattice were analysed to determine the structures within the GP zones and their transformation pathway.

To compare the thermodynamic stabilities of structures with varying Al content, the formation enthalpy was expressed in eV/atom of solute atoms, instead of eV/atom. This transformation is achieved as follows:

$$\Delta H_{form}^{solute}(Al_{1-x-y}Mg_xSi_yAg_z) = \frac{H_{form}}{x_{Mg} + y_{Si} + z_{Ag}} \quad (15)$$

where H_{form} is the formation enthalpy of configurations, which was calculated from eq. (1). The use of this transformation enables the projection of the three-dimensional common tangent hull onto a two-dimensional plane. The convex hull of ΔH_{form}^{solute} is plotted as a function of $x_{Mg} + y_{Si} + z_{Ag}$ in Fig. 6(a). Generally, structures on the convex hull are considered stable and potential GP zones. Several orderings fall on the convex hulls of ΔH_{form}^{solute} , suggesting that the ordered GP zones in the Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloys may have multiple structures, depending on the local composition ratio among solutes. The ΔH_{form}^{solute} for configuration with $x_{Mg} + y_{Si} + z_{Ag} = 1$ is plotted in Fig. 6(b). We noticed that all structures - except for Mg_3Si - that lie on the convex hull are composed of Al, Mg and Ag atoms, which differs significantly from those found in Al-Mg-Si alloys. This indicates the crystal structures of GP zones may be changed by adding Ag, and their transformation pathway can be modified as follows: Ag atoms initially replace Al atoms in the fcc-Al matrix to form a series of Ag_zAl_{1-z} solid solutions. Subsequently, both Al and Ag atoms in the Ag_zAl_{1-z} structures are progressively substituted by Mg atoms, leading to the formation of $Ag_zAl_{1-x-z}Mg_x$ structures. Eventually, all Al atoms are replaced by Mg, resulting in the formation of Ag_zMg_x structures.

Fig. 6 (a) Formation enthalpy per solute atom, ΔH_{form}^{solute} , calculated from eq. (15) as a function of $x_{Mg} + y_{Si} + z_{Ag}$. (b) ΔH_{form}^{solute} as a function of z_{Ag} for configurations with $x_{Mg} + y_{Si} + z_{Ag} = 1$.

3.5 Phase stability at elevated temperatures

3.5.1 Comparison with MC and MC-fitted TDB

The CE of each lattice structure can be used to predict the thermodynamic properties of the corresponding structures with this lattice, following the methodology presented in Section 2.3. The compositional grid of the Al-Mg-Si-Ag quaternary system for fcc and β lattice was systematically explored using an interval of 10 at.% for each one of the constituents. The β' and β'_{Ag} only exist in a small compositional range, so the interval of 3.5 at.% for each component is used. Gibbs free energies of formation G_{form} for each composition were calculated as indicated in Section 2.3. In the end, G_{form} as a function of composition at elevated temperatures was fitted as indicated in Section 2.4 to develop TDBs of Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloys. The G_{form} at 500 K obtained using MC-fitted TDB and those calculated directly from MC simulations were first compared in the six binary systems underlying fcc and β lattice to verify the accuracy of TDBs, as shown in Fig. 7. The G_{form} obtained using MC-fitted TDB is in good agreement with those calculated from MC simulations in the six binary systems. The fcc phase is more stable than β in the whole composition range for Ag-Al, Ag-Mg and Al-Mg binary systems. The stability of the phase changed between fcc and β phase in the whole composition range for Ag-Si, Al-Si and Mg-Si binary systems. Such as the fcc phase is more stable than the β phase in the Ag-rich Ag-Si and Al-rich Al-Si. The β phase is more stable than the fcc phase in the Si composition larger than 0.2 for the Mg-Si binary system.

Additionally, the G_{form} at 500 K obtained from MC-fitted TDB and MC simulations in the pseudo-binary systems, such as the composition of Al and Mg are fixed, are also compared and

shown in Fig. 8. It should be noted that only G_{form} obtained using MC-fitted TDB for fcc and β lattice are depicted in Fig. 8. The β' and β'_{Ag} phases can co-exist with the fcc phase in this composition range. It should be noted that there are some differences between MC and MC-fitted TDB for β'_{Ag} lattice, which may be improved by performing MC simulations on a denser compositional grid. In fact, the MC-fitted TDB remains suitable for calculating the G_{form} of this lattice. This is supported by the low CV score of 0.0061 eV/atom, calculated based on the G_{form} from MC and MC-fitted TDB. The G_{form} at 300 K and 800 K obtained from the two approaches can be found in Figs. S1-S4 in the Supplementary Material. Except for a small difference in the G_{form} of β'_{Ag} lattice, the G_{form} for fcc, β and β' lattices obtained using MC-fitted TDB are in good agreement with those calculated directly from MC simulations. The TDBs for the temperature range from 100 K to 1000 K were constructed using the Calphad method based on the G_{form} obtained from the MC simulation. These databases are provided in the Supplementary Material as a compressed file named TDB.zip, which includes individual TDB files for each temperature interval: Al-Mg-Si-Ag-100K.TDB, Al-Mg-Si-Ag-200K.TDB, ... , up to Al-Mg-Si-Ag-1000K.TDB.

Fig. 7. The comparison of Gibbs free energies of formation G_{form} calculated from MC simulations and the OpenCalphad calculations using TDB based on MC simulations at 500 K for (a) Ag-Al. (b) Ag-Mg. (c) Ag-Si. (d) Al-Mg. (e) Al-Si and (f) Mg-Si binary systems underlying fcc and β lattice. Green and orange circles represent the G_{form} with fcc and β lattice calculated from MC simulations, respectively. Green and orange lines represent the G_{form} with fcc and β lattice calculated using TDB, respectively.

Fig. 8. The comparison of Gibbs free energies of formation G_{form} calculated from MC simulations and the OpenCalphad calculations using TDB based on MC simulations at 500 K for (a) $\text{Ag}_{0.339-x}\text{Al}_{0.0357}\text{Mg}_{0.607}\text{Si}_x$ and (b) $\text{Ag}_{0.296-x}\text{Al}_{0.037}\text{Mg}_{0.63}\text{Si}_x$ pseudo-binary systems underlying fcc, β , β' and β'_{Ag} lattice. Green and orange lines represent the G_{form} with fcc and β lattice calculated using TDB, respectively. Purple circles and lines represent the G_{form} with β' or β'_{Ag} lattice calculated from MC simulations and the TDB, respectively.

3.5.2 fcc, β , β' and β'_{Ag} phase distribution

The methodology based on the development of TDBs and their implementations in the OpenCalphad calculations, as described in Section 2.4, was used to investigate the distribution of different phases and their fractions in Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloys. As mentioned in Section 2.3, the phase composition is determined using the common tangent of Gibbs free energy of formation G_{form} , and the phase fractions are subsequently calculated using the lever rule.

The percentage of fcc phase across the whole composition range at 300 K is plotted in Fig. 9(a), while the corresponding phase distribution is depicted in Fig. 9(b). The phase composition is plotted in different colors, each indicating the stability region of the four different phases. It is well known that the stable structure of Si and Mg is diamond and hcp lattice, thus they are only located on the vertices of the tetrahedron and plotted in grey and pink circles in Fig. 9(b), (d) and (f). Furthermore, the β' and β'_{Ag} phases are not analyzed separately in this work because they always co-exist at the over-aging stage [19]. It can also be seen that the Gibbs free energy of formation G_{form} for them with similar composition is very close. In the end, only the fcc solid solution (the fcc phase percentage is 100%) appeared in the Al-Mg, Ag-Mg, Al-Ag binary systems, and one Al-Mg-Ag ternary system. The same results are also observed at 500 K (Fig. 9(c)) and 800 K (Fig. 9(c)), indicating that the ordering states are easily formed among Al, Mg

and Ag atoms. The percentage of fcc phase decreased with temperature from 800 K (Fig. 9(e)) to 300 K (Fig. 9(e)), indicating some other phases precipitated from the Al matrix. It can be seen from the phase distribution that the single β phase region is observed in the Si-rich Ag-Mg-Si and Al-Mg-Si ternary systems at 500 K (Fig. 9(d)) and 800 K (Fig. 9(f)). The β phase coexists with fcc and β' or β'_{Ag} phase in the Al-Mg-Si ternary system at 300 K (Fig. 9(b)). However, it is not easy to analyse the phase change in the interior from a four-dimensional phase diagram, so a more detailed analysis will be described in Section 3.5.3.

Fig. 9 Percentage of fcc phase and different phase distribution obtained from OpenCalphad calculations at 300 K (a), (b), 500 K (c), (d) and 800 K (e), (f).

3.5.3 Phase stability in the Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloys

The fcc fractions and phase distribution for Al-Mg-Si ternary alloys -computed using the OpenCalphad calculations based on MC-fitted TDB as described in Section 2.4- are shown in Fig. 10. There is a high fcc fraction ($>70\%$) in the Al-rich part of the Al-Mg-Si phase diagram, whether at 300 K (Fig. 10(a)), 500 K (Fig. 10(c)) or 800 K (Fig. 10(e)). In parallel, a low fcc fraction ($<20\%$) is also observed in the Si-rich part of the Al-Mg-Si phase diagram from three different temperatures (Fig. 10(a), (c) and (e)). The phase compositions of the stability region at 300 K, 500K and 800 K are plotted in Fig. 10(b), (d) and (f), respectively. A $fcc+\beta$ two-phase

region plotted in green color is found in the Mg-rich part at 300 K (Fig. 10(b)). It can be seen that there is a high fcc fraction (>60%) in this two-phase region, and the fcc fraction has a slight change as temperature increases to 800 K (Fig. 10(e)), indicating that the fcc phase remains thermodynamically stable over this temperature range. The stable $\beta+\beta'$ two-phase region is plotted in purple color, and the $\text{fcc}+\beta'$ two-phase region is plotted in red color. There is a $\text{fcc}+\beta+\beta'$ three-phase region that is plotted in brown color. As the temperature increases, these regions gradually transform into a two-phase region where fcc and β coexist.

To figure out the effect of Ag on the phase stability, the fcc fractions and phase distribution for $(\text{AlMgSi})_{90}\text{Ag}_{10}$ composition are analyzed and also compared with Al-Mg-Si in Fig. 11. The stable two-phase regions changed from $\text{fcc}+\beta'$ (or $\beta+\beta'$) to $\text{fcc}+\beta'/\beta'_{\text{Ag}}$ (or $\beta+\beta'/\beta'_{\text{Ag}}$) when Ag is added into Al-Mg-Si alloys, indicating that the addition of Ag improves the stability of β' phase. As temperature increases from 300 K (Fig. 11(a), (c)) to 500 K (Fig. 11(b), (d)), the $\text{fcc}+\beta'/\beta'_{\text{Ag}}$ two-phase regions in the Mg-rich part gradually transform into the $\text{fcc}+\beta$ two-phase region, while the stable $\beta+\beta'/\beta'_{\text{Ag}}$ two-phase regions in the Si-rich part completely transform into the $\text{fcc}+\beta$ two-phase region and a small single β phase region. As temperature increases to 800 K (Fig. 11(e), (f)), except for the $\text{fcc}+\beta'/\beta'_{\text{Ag}}$ two-phase region in the Al-rich gradually transforms into the $\text{fcc}+\beta$ two-phase region, the $\text{fcc}+\beta+\beta'/\beta'_{\text{Ag}}$ three-phase region also partly converts into the $\text{fcc}+\beta$ two-phase region. Additionally, only the fcc single-phase region (blue color) appeared in the Al-Mg-Ag ternary system at three different temperatures (Fig. 11(b), (d) and (f)), indicating that Al-Mg-Ag is more likely to form atomic clusters in the Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloys. A significant difference in the fcc fraction was observed between Fig.10(a) and Fig. 11(a), particularly in the Mg-rich part. It can be seen that there is a $\text{fcc}+\beta$ two-phase region in the Mg-rich part in Fig.11(b), while the stable two-phase region is $\text{fcc}+\beta'/\beta'_{\text{Ag}}$ in Fig. 11(b). This indicates that β' or β'_{Ag} is more stable than β in this composition range. The fcc fractions and phase distribution for $(\text{AlMgSi})_{70}\text{Ag}_{30}$ can be found in Fig. S5 in the supplementary Materials. The stable phase region in this composition range at 300 K (Fig. S5(a), (b)) is composed of $\text{fcc}+\beta+\beta'/\beta'_{\text{Ag}}$ three-phase region and $\text{fcc}+\beta'/\beta'_{\text{Ag}}$ two-phase region. As temperature increases to 500 K (Fig. S5(b), (c)), they are gradually transformed into the $\text{fcc}+\beta$ two-phase region. As temperature increases to 800 K (Fig. S5(e), (f)), the stable phase region is dominated by the $\text{fcc}+\beta$ two-phase region, and there is a single fcc phase region observed in the Al-rich part.

Fig. 10. Fcc fraction and phase distribution in the Al-Mg-Si ternary phase diagram at 300 K (a), (b), 500 K (c), (d) and 800 K (e), (f).

Fig. 11. Fcc fraction and phase distribution in the $(\text{AlMgSi})_{90}\text{Ag}_{10}$ pseudo-ternary phase diagram at 300 K (a), (b), 500 K (c), (d) and 800 K (e), (f).

4. Discussion

4.1 Effect of Ag on the solute clusters

It is well known from the precipitation sequence of Al-Mg-Si-based alloys that solute clusters were first precipitated from SSSS. These clusters serve as precursors to influence the artificial ageing response and govern the transformation pathways of the precipitation sequence. However, in contrast to the detailed knowledge of metastable precipitates - structures, evolution,

and their influence on material properties -, the knowledge about the atomic clusters that preceded them is very limited. Therefore, to figure out the effect of Ag on the solute clusters in the Al-Mg-Si alloys, a fcc solid solution with the composition $\text{Al}_{98}\text{Mg}_1\text{Si}_1$ (at.%) - same as experiments - was generated using the SQS method and then used to perform MC simulations, as described in Section 2.3. In parallel, a series of fcc solid solution models with varying Ag composition, ranging from 0.1 at. % to 1 at. % in increments of 0.1 at. %, were also generated to perform MC simulations. These models were used to compare the clustering behaviors with those of the Ag-free fcc solid solution.

Formation enthalpies H_{form}^{MC} of each solid solution model as a function of temperature were calculated using eq. (2), as shown in Fig. 12 (a). H_{form}^{MC} is a constant for Ag-free fcc solid solution above 180 K, indicating that it is a completely disordered state. H_{form}^{MC} decreases sharply below 180 K, and it might form local chemical clustering and short-range ordering because there are differences in the atomic bonding between elements under the enthalpy effect. As Ag concentration increases, the temperature at which the H_{form}^{MC} starts to significantly decrease shifts to a higher temperatures. For instance, H_{form}^{MC} of $\text{Al}_{97.9}\text{Mg}_1\text{Si}_1\text{Ag}_{0.1}$ starts to decrease significantly at 230 K, $\text{Al}_{97}\text{Mg}_1\text{Si}_1\text{Ag}_{0.5}$ at 420 K and $\text{Al}_{97}\text{Mg}_1\text{Si}_1\text{Ag}_1$ at 480 K. The atomic model where H_{form}^{MC} drops sharply is drawn in the Fig. 12(b)-(e). Al atoms are not visualized in these figures to show more clearly the clustering of solute atoms. A Mg-Si co-cluster is formed in the $\text{Al}_{98}\text{Mg}_1\text{Si}_1$ model (Fig. 12(b)). Mg-Si co-clusters have been observed in the early stage in the Al-Mg-Si alloy by three-dimensional atom probe (3DAP) and TEM [6]. The cluster type changed by adding Ag to Al-Mg-Si alloys, even if the amount of Ag is very small, and the Mg-Si-Ag co-clusters are formed in $\text{Al}_{97.9}\text{Mg}_1\text{Si}_1\text{Ag}_{0.1}$ (Fig. 12(c)). As the Ag concentration increases to 0.5 at. % (Fig. 12(d)), the Mg-Ag co-clusters are dominant at 420 K in $\text{Al}_{97.9}\text{Mg}_1\text{Si}_1\text{Ag}_{0.5}$, while Si atoms exist in a disordered state. Si atoms entered Mg-Ag co-clusters and Mg-Si-Ag co-clusters are formed when the temperature decreased to 200 K, as shown in Fig. S6(a) in the supplementary material. Similar clustering behavior is also observed in $\text{Al}_{97.9}\text{Mg}_1\text{Si}_1\text{Ag}_1$ (Fig. 12(e) and Fig. S6(b)).

Fig. 12 (a) Formation enthalpies $H_{\text{form}}^{\text{MC}}$ with varying Ag concentration as a function of temperature calculated by eq. (2). Solute clusters in the fcc solid solution with the Ag concentration of 0 at.% (b), 0.1 at.% (c), 0.5 at.% (d) and 1.0 at.% (e), respectively.

The effect of Cu on the clustering behaviour in the Al-Mg-Si alloys has been widely studied [74-76]. They found that although the solute cluster was dominated by Mg-Si clusters although

Mg-Si-Cu clusters were formed at the earlier aging stage. Obviously, the cluster formation mechanism in Al-Mg-Si-Cu alloys is not completely applicable to Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloys. Here, the short-range order (SRO) parameter [79] provides a quantitative measure of the extent to which atomic pair distributions deviate from a completely random arrangement, which can be used to explain the solute clustering behaviors in Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloys. SRO can be obtained from the relation of pair probabilities and point probabilities using the following expression:

$$\alpha_n^{AB} = 1 - \frac{y_{2,n}^{AB}}{c_A c_B} \quad (16)$$

where $y_{2,n}^{AB}$ is the pair probability function for chosen atomic species, c_A and c_B are concentrations of chosen atomic species. A more detailed description can be found in [34,45]. The SRO parameters for various atomic pairs in the first nearest-neighbor (1NN) shell of fcc solid solution are shown in Fig. 13. In $\text{Al}_{98}\text{Mg}_1\text{Si}_1$ (Fig. 13(a)), only the Mg-Si pair exhibits a negative SRO parameter, indicating that there is a strong interaction between Mg and Si atoms, which leads to the formation of Mg-Si clusters. For $\text{Al}_{97.5}\text{Mg}_1\text{Si}_1\text{Ag}_{0.5}$ (Fig. 13(b)), negative SRO parameters are also found for the Mg-Ag and Ag-Si pairs. This reflects the tendency for local clustering among Mg, Si, and Ag atoms. Notably, the SRO parameter for the Mg-Ag pair is more negative than that for the Mg-Si pair, which may be the main reason for the preferential formation of Mg-Ag co-clusters. Additionally, the binding energies reported in [80] follow this trend: $\text{Ag-Mg} > \text{Mg-Si} > \text{Si-Ag}$, which aligns with our results and further supports the higher likelihood of Ag-Mg co-cluster formation.

Fig. 13 SRO parameters in the first nearest-neighbor (1NN) shell for the fcc solid solution $\text{Al}_{98}\text{Mg}_1\text{Si}_1$ (a) and $\text{Al}_{97.5}\text{Mg}_1\text{Si}_1\text{Ag}_{0.5}$ (b).

4.2 Effect of Ag on the stability of β''

The metastable β'' phase is recognized as the most effective strengthening precipitate in aged Al-Mg-Si and Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloys. The β'' phase has a monoclinic crystal structure that is closely related to the Al matrix, as shown in Fig. 1(b), but its chemical composition has not been uniquely determined. The likely composition of β'' contains $Mg_5Al_2Si_4$, $Mg_4Al_3Si_4$ and Mg_5Si_6 [81]. Additionally, it is well known that Ag facilitates the formation of clusters at the early aging stage. High density of clusters results in a finer and denser distribution of β'' phase and thus improves the peak hardness for these alloys [19]. It has been observed from experiments that Ag atoms preferentially segregate at the β''/α -Al interfaces at the peak aging condition by the replacement of Al atoms in the fcc matrix [82]. However, the effect of Ag on the structure of β'' precipitates in the Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloy is unclear. Thus, the formation enthalpies H_{form} of β'' with varying composition of $Al_{1-x-y-z}Mg_xSi_yAg_z$ ($z < 0.25$) were calculated based on DFT, as shown in Fig. 14(a). It should be pointed out that each β'' configuration has the same lattice parameters as Mg_5Si_6 , but has different atomic occupations. The H_{form} with a composition of $Al_5Mg_2Si_4$ is the lowest with 0.0106 eV/atom. Although there is a small difference between $Al_5Mg_2Si_4$ and $Ag_4AlMg_{10}Si_7$ (lowest H_{form}), H_{form} of $Al_{1-x-y-z}Mg_xSi_yAg_z$ is always higher than H_{form} of $Al_5Mg_2Si_4$. This indicates that the incorporation of Ag atom into β'' is energetically unfavorable.

To figure out the crystal structure and the formation pathway of β'' , the H_{form} of $Al_{1-x-y}Mg_xSi_y$ configurations was analysed based on the results of Fig. 14(a). Similarly with eq. (15), the formation enthalpy is also expressed in eV/atom of solute atoms as:

$$\Delta H_{form}^{solute}(Al_{1-x-y}Mg_xSi_y) = \frac{H_{form}}{x_{Mg} + y_{Si}} \quad (17)$$

where H_{form} is formation enthalpy of configurations, which was calculated from eq. (1). The convex hull of ΔH_{form}^{solute} are plotted as a function of $x_{Mg}/x_{Mg} + y_{Si}$ in Fig. 14(b). The structure that lies on the convex hull is considered stable and the most likely to transform into Mg_5Si_6 . It can be seen that there may be two different pathways to form β'' . In the first one is, the Al atoms in the $Al_5Mg_2Si_4$ are replaced firstly by Si atoms to form $Al_3Mg_2Si_6$, and then replaced by Mg atoms to form Mg_5Si_6 . This path, $Al_5Mg_2Si_4 \rightarrow Al_3Mg_2Si_6 \rightarrow Mg_5Si_6$, was observed in [83]. The second one is $Al_4Mg_5Si_2 \rightarrow Al_3Mg_5Si_3 \rightarrow Al_2Mg_5Si_4 \rightarrow Mg_5Si_6$, where Al atoms are only replaced by Si. Additionally, the energies of Al-rich solid solution are estimated by the tie-line connecting the energies of isolated Si or Mg impurities in Al matrix (orange circles in Fig.

14(b)). All predicted energies are below the tie-lines, indicating that there are enthalpically driven to form from solid solutions [84]. It is also noticed that Mg_4Si_7 lies on the convex hull, but this has not been reported experimentally.

Fig. 14 (a) Formation enthalpies H_{form} of β'' with vary composition of $Al_{1-x-y-z}Mg_xSi_yAg_z$ ($z < 0.25$) calculated based on DFT. (b) Formation enthalpies per solute atom ΔH_{form}^{solute} as a function of $x_{Mg}/x_{Mg} + y_{Si}$. Green circles represent formation enthalpies of β'' configurations, orange circles represent formation enthalpies of Mg (or Si) in fcc-Al solid solution.

4.4 STEM observations of aged Al0.89Mg0.96Si0.15Ag alloy

Fig. 15 gathers the HAADF-STEM images of early-stage clustering and evolution of precipitates during artificial ageing. Clusters are expected to feature the fcc phase. Thus, no distortions in the lattice images associated with new periodicities could reveal their presence. Indeed, the HAADF-STEM image taken during the EDS scans (Fig. 15 (a)) shows the perfect four-fold symmetry periodicity of [001] oriented Al matrix. The Z-contrast related to the heavier Ag atoms suggests that they take the positions of Al atoms in the fcc lattice. EDS mapping of chemical elements confirms that brighter regions are enriched with the presence of Ag. Additionally, Mg is also located around the same regions (marked with the circle), suggesting the formation of Mg-Ag co-clusters. The distribution of Si is not so straightforward, however, and it is not homogeneous also. Thus, it may be expected that some diffusion-based processes, leading to the incorporation of Si into clusters, had already begun at this stage of ageing. After 2h of ageing (Fig.15(b)), very fine β'' precipitates are observed. This image presents the cross section of the needle-shaped precipitates, revealing a single monoclinic unit cell of the β'' phase. The white contrast on the top of the precipitate is related to the segregation of Ag atoms outside the precipitate, as predicted by our models. After long artificial ageing (up to 12h), the β'' precipitates grow, as can be noticed in Fig. 15(c). Although, the diffusion-based

phenomena allowed the growth of the precipitate, the Ag atoms are still not entering the unit cell of β'' most likely due to an energetic barrier, as predicted by our results in Fig. 14(a).

Fig. 15 HAADF-STEM imaging of clusters and precipitates in $\text{Al}_{0.89}\text{Mg}_{0.96}\text{Si}_{0.15}\text{Ag}$ alloy after various ageing times (a) HAADF image and EDS maps of the elements distribution after 0.5h of artificial ageing (b) Cross-section of β'' phase with Ag segregation after 2h of artificial ageing (c) the well-established β'' precipitate in the peak-ageing condition - 12h

5. Conclusions

The effect of Ag on phase stability and distribution of precipitates was investigated using a comprehensive strategy that integrates first-principles calculations, cluster expansion coupled with Monte Carlo simulations, and the Calphad approach. Specifically, the formation enthalpies of different configurations for various lattices across the Al-Mg-Si-Ag system were calculated by density functional theory. These formation enthalpies were fitted with a cluster expansion that was employed to calculate the Gibbs free energy of formation as a function of temperature in the whole composition region by means of Monte Carlo simulations. The Gibbs free energies of formation were used to create a thermodynamic database for the Al-Mg-Si-Ag system. Finally, the results of our investigation were confirmed through HAADF-STEM.

Our results showed that the solute cluster was dominated by Mg-Si co-clusters in Al-Mg-Si alloys, whereas Mg-Ag co-clusters formed prior to the Mg-Si-Ag clusters when the Al-Mg-Si-Ag alloy was quenched from high temperatures. This difference can be attributed to the SRO parameter for the Mg-Ag pair, which is more negative than that for the Mg-Si pair. The addition of Ag also alters the crystal structure of GP zones, which follow a transformation sequence of $\text{Ag}_z\text{Al}_{1-z} \rightarrow \text{Ag}_z\text{Al}_{1-x-z}\text{Mg}_x \rightarrow \text{Ag}_z\text{Mg}_x$. However, the crystal structures of metastable phase β'' and stable phase β remain unaffected by Ag addition because they are energetically unfavorable. There may be two pathways for the formation of metastable phase β'' : either $\text{Al}_5\text{Mg}_2\text{Si}_4 \rightarrow \text{Al}_3\text{Mg}_2\text{Si}_6 \rightarrow \text{Mg}_5\text{Si}_6$ or $\text{Al}_4\text{Mg}_5\text{Si}_2 \rightarrow \text{Al}_3\text{Mg}_5\text{Si}_3 \rightarrow \text{Al}_2\text{Mg}_5\text{Si}_4 \rightarrow \text{Mg}_5\text{Si}_6$.

The calculated Al-Mg-Si-Ag phase diagrams shows a fcc single-phase region in Al-Ag, Al-Mg, and Ag-Mg binaries as well as in the Al-Ag-Mg ternary system. The fcc+ β two-phase region and the fcc+ $\beta'/\beta'_{\text{Ag}}$ region appeared in the Al-rich Al-Mg-Si-Ag system. Additionally, as temperature increases, the fcc+ $\beta'/\beta'_{\text{Ag}}$ two-phase region gradually transforms into the fcc+ β two-phase region.

HAADF-STEM imaging combined with EDS elemental mapping revealed the formation of Mg-Ag co-clusters which evolve into monoclinic β'' phase with Ag segregation at interfacial boundaries, which is in good agreement with our simulation results.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

W. Shao: Methodology, investigation, writing original draft, writing review/editing. **W. Chrominski:** Investigation, writing original draft, writing review/editing. **M. Fedorov:** Investigation, writing review/editing. **C.Y. Shi:** Investigation, writing review/editing. **J.**

LLorca: Methodology, conceptualization, writing review/editing. **J. S. Wróbel:** Methodology, conceptualization, writing original draft, writing review/editing.

Declaration of Interest Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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